

DEL 3.2 Measuring
temperature and
kinetic fields during
FSW, AM and broaching

enable

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Deliverable 3.2 - ESR 7

"Employed methodology for temperature and kinematic fields measurements during orthogonal cutting"

1. Introduction

The deliverable 3.2 "Employed methodology for temperature and kinetic field's measurements during orthogonal cutting" is the third deliverable in the WP3. This document is set to describe the experimental set up. It details the metallographic preparation of the specimens and the tools implementation for temperature and kinematic field's measurements during orthogonal cutting. It ends with presenting the obtained results and its analysis.

In the next sections, the following points will be described with more details:

- 🌈 Metallographic preparation of the specimens.
- 🌈 Experimental set up.
- 🌈 Implementation of the experimental protocol.
- 🌈 Results and analysis.

2. Metallographic preparation of the specimens

2.1 Initial microstructure of the metallic alloys to be analyzed in ENABLE

🌈 Initial Microstructure of Ti-6Al-4V

The Ti-6Al-4V is composed nearly of 6% of aluminum and 4% of vanadium. Titanium has the maximum percentage (Nearly 88,98 of Ti and 0,156% of Fe in Ti-6Al-4V alloy [Julien 2017]). For the case of this alloy, the microstructure obtained depends on the nature of the thermomechanical treatment undergone by the material [Vila, 2010]. This treatment process is composed of 4 steps: (I) Homogenization, (II) Deformation, (III) Recrystallization and (IV) Aging.

Lamellar microstructure: It is obtained if the recrystallization stage is made in the β domain and followed by quenching with water. The recrystallization temperature is a temperature higher by 30-50 ° C relative to the β transus temperature. The cooling rate affects the size and the number of lamellae α . With low cooling rate, we obtain a needled microstructure characterized by the existence of martensitic needles α' . With high cooling rate, the resulting microstructure is completely lamellar [Figure 1-a], also called Widmanstätten.

This structure is composed of lamellar colonies $\alpha+\beta$. Depending on colonies orientations, various shear phenomena were observed. Four configurations were then proposed in [Wagner 2017] to describe the shear band formation.

"Equiaxed" microstructure: It is obtained after recrystallization in the $\alpha + \beta$ domain followed by slow cooling. This treatment promotes the appearance of spherical nodules α . The "equiaxed" microstructure is given in Figure 1-b.

Duplex microstructure: This microstructure [Figure 1-c] is a combination of lamellar and "equiaxed" microstructure. It is the result of cooling at a moderate speed. The main parameter of the treatment process is the cooling rate from step (I), because it determines the width of α lamellae that will be deformed and recrystallized in the next steps (Deformation and recrystallization). In the step (II), the lamellar structure is deformed plastically in the $\alpha+\beta$ phase with enough stored energy that lead to a complete recrystallization of the α and β phase in the step (III) [Vila 2010]. In step (III), temperature has an important effect. It determines the volume fraction of recrystallized equiaxed α .

Figure 1: Different microstructures of Ti-6Al-4V alloy.

Note that the grain size plays an important role on the mechanical properties [Nouari, 2013]. More grain size is fine, better are the mechanical properties. This is explained by the large number of grain boundaries that block dislocation movements [Ramirez, 2017].

Furthermore, [Wagner 2017] found that, for the case of lamellar structure, the shear band formation depends not only from the generated shear strain but also from the different colonies orientations.

Initial microstructure of Inconel 718

Inconel 718 used in the aeronautical, space and nuclear industries is considered to be a refractory superalloy. It contains a large amount of nickel: between 50 and 55%, and chromium: between 17 and 21%. The operating temperatures of this alloy are above 600 ° C.

The microstructure of Inconel 718 is characterized by: The matrix γ , the phase γ' , the phase γ'' , the phase δ and the carbide phase MC: Iron, chromium and cobalt combine with nickel to form the matrix γ . The crystallographic structure of the matrix and the two phases is given in figure 2. Phase γ' and γ'' are present in small proportions and are consistent with matrix γ . The matrix γ has a cubic face-centered structure. Phases γ and γ' are hardening phases of the alloy. Containing carburigenic elements, this stimulates the appearance of carbides (Ti, Cr, Nb, Mo, C, B) generally observed in grain boundaries [Zemzemi 2007; Le Coz 2012].

Figure 2: Crystallographic structure of the matrix γ and The two phases γ' and γ'' [Zemzemi 2007].

The heat treatment undergone by this alloy will therefore modify its microstructure. [Siu 2011] extracted specimens from a forged and heat-treated piece. For a heat treatment at $T = 1100^\circ\text{C}$ maintained for 10 min, the micrographic observation shows the microstructure of Inconel 718 which reveals grains of 40 μm size [Figure 3].

Figure 3: Microstructure of Inconel 718: a) Non treated and b) Forged and treated at $T=1100^\circ\text{C}$ for 10min, [Siu 2011].

Initial microstructure of Al7075-T6

Aeronautical aluminum alloys are used in the aerospace industry as structural parts materials. The series used are 2xxx, 3xxx, 5xxx, 6xxx, and 7xxx. 2xxx series are suitable for high service temperatures. 3xxx, 5xxx and 6xxx alloys are used as examples in hydraulic and lubrication mechanisms and require high mechanical strength. For 7xxx alloys, they are suitable for low service temperatures and are mounted in mechanisms that also require high mechanical strength [Alu Quebec]. Here we are interested in 7xxx type alloys and in particular Al7075-T651 alloy. It contains zinc, magnesium and copper to maximize its resistance.

The microstructure of an extruded Al 7075 aluminum alloy can be characterized by elongated grains in the extrusion direction. The microstructural evolution following a quenching test which consists of heating at a temperature T , maintain it for 7 min and after cooling it in water is described in [Rokni 2011]. Experimental temperatures are $T = 450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $520\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $580\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The microstructure observed after heat treatment is given by the following figure:

Figure 4: Microstructure of Al7075-T6 after quenching test: a) $T=450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, b) $T=500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, c) $T=520\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, d) $T=550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and e) $T=580\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, [Rokni 2011].

Microscopically, grains and grain boundaries are best observed after treatment at $T = 550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T = 580\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

2.2 Polishing and etching

In order to apply the digital image correlation to determine the kinematic fields, surface preparation of each specimen should be made to reveal the present phases.

Difficulty of metallographic preparation of Ti-6Al-4V: During cutting, overheating can take place. Also, because of its high ductility, Ti-6AL-4V is difficult to cut. For polishing, this can easily generate scratches.

Employed method for metallographic preparation:

1/ Use of diamond cutting wheels.

2/ Polishing: The polishing is divided into two steps:

The first step is plane polishing under water lubrication and with a rotation speed equal to 300rpm. The used abrasive papers are as follow:

For Al7075 workpiece:

- 🎨 P120.
- 🎨 P400.
- 🎨 P800.
- 🎨 P1200.
- 🎨 Silicon carbide 800/2400.

For Ti-6Al-4V workpiece:

- 🎨 P80.
- 🎨 P120.
- 🎨 P400.
- 🎨 P1200.
- 🎨 Silicon carbide 800/1200.
- 🎨 Silicon carbide 1200/4000.

The second step after plane polishing is the fine polishing with a rotation speed equal to 150rpm using the following papers:

🎨 PadRam paper under the diamond suspension GEL2+ monocrystalline 3 μ solution as lubricant.

🎨 PadSupra with a lubricant solution as follow:

- For Al7075 workpiece: 30ml of non-crystallizing colloidal silica + 20ml of water.
- For Ti-6Al-4V workpiece: 20ml of non-crystallizing colloidal silica + 10ml of water + 10ml of H₂O₂.

3/ chemical attack

For the Al7075 workpiece, the chemical attack was made by Keller solution for 30s. For 1L, this solution contains 955ml of H₂O, 25ml of HNO₃, 15ml of HCl and 5ml of HF.

For the Ti-6Al-4V, it was made by Kroll solution for 20s. For 1L, this solution contains 960ml of H₂O, 30ml of HNO₃ and 10ml of HF.

2.3 Obtained microstructure

After polishing specimens, the obtained microstructure are given in the following figures. Three specimens of Ti-6Al-4V with different microstructures and one of Al7075-T6 were polished.

- Ti-6Al-4V with globular microstructure

Figure 5: Ti-6Al-4V with globular microstructure: a) X5 magnification, b) X20 magnification and c) X50 magnification.

- Ti-6Al-4V with "equiaxed" microstructure

Figure 6: Ti-6Al-4V with "equiaxed" microstructure: a) X5 magnification, b) X20 magnification and c) X50 magnification.

- Ti-6Al-4V with lamellar microstructure

Figure 7: Ti-6Al-4V with lamellar microstructure: a) X5 magnification, b) X20 magnification and c) X50 magnification.

- Al7075-T6 microstructure

Figure 8: Al7075-T6 microstructure: a) X5 magnification, b) X20 magnification and c) X50 magnification.

3. Experimental set up

3.1 Tools and operative parameters

- Cutting tools:

Two different cutting tools made of tungsten carbide WC will be used for the orthogonal cutting tests on Ti-6Al-4V and Inconel 718. The rake angles are 0° and 15° . These angles will be used to study their influences on the chip morphology as well as the evolution of the measured kinematic and thermal fields. The same tools will be used for tests on the Al7075 aluminum alloy. The choice on the rake angles of 0° and 15° was made to be able to compare the obtained cutting efforts, kinematic and thermal field's measurements as well as the chip morphology with the results of [Calamaz 2008, Calamaz 2010, Calamaz 2011, Cotterell 2008a and b, Miguélez 2013, Ye 2013, Pottier 2014, Melkote 2015, Yaich 2015, Zhang 2015, Harzallah 2018]. The employed rake angles in these publications with the cutting speed are summarized in the following table:

Publication	Workpiece material	Cutting speed	rake angle
[Calamaz 2008], [Calamaz 2010], and [Calamaz 2011]	Ti-6Al-4V	60m/min	-4°
[Cotterell 2008a and b]		4-120m/min	$6,5^\circ$
[Miguélez 2013]		<60m/min	0°
[Ye 2013]		3 and 60m/min	0°
[Pottier 2014]		6m/min	0°
[Melkote 2015]		20 and 60m/min	0°
[Yaich 2015]		75m/min	2°
[Zhang 2015]		90m/min	0°
[Harzallah, 2018]		3 and 15m/min	0° and 15°

Table 1: Employed cutting speed and rake angle in the mentioned publication.

- Insert holders:

Two insert holders will be used. A 0° insert holder and a 15° one. The insert holder contains a groove where it is located the insert which will be blocked by clamping the screw.

 Insert:

Two inserts were anticipated to be used in these experiments: S4 and H13A. In this inserts, the rake face is parallel to the opposite bottom face.

The clearance angle of the used insert was measured using the KEYENCE microscopy. The geometrical parameter of the tool are given in the table 2.

Tool with insert H13A	λ ($^{\circ}$)	α ($^{\circ}$)	R (μm)
	0	11 $^{\circ}$	---

λ : Cutting angle.
 α : Clearance angle.
 R: Sharpness radius.

Table 2: Geometrical parameters of the used tool.

3.2 Instrumentations for in-situ measurements

3.2.1 Cutting efforts measurements

The cutting efforts will be measured using a 6 components dynamometer 9257B. Three effort components in the orthogonal cutting [Figure 9] are interesting to be analysed. Validation of numerical models is based at first on the comparison between the obtained numerical and experimental cutting efforts. Also, they can be used to predict the power consumption and to study the tool wear.

- The cutting force F_x .
- The feed force F_z .
- Torque around Y axis.

Figure 9: Orthogonal cutting configuration.

3.2.2 Criteria for the selection of high speed camera

- Frame rate/ Spatial resolution

For a more detailed description of the evolution of the kinematic quantities (displacements, strain and strain rate) at the level of the adiabatic shear bands, it is necessary to guarantee a rather high frame rate with respect to the chip segmentation frequencies. This will allow to have a certain number of visual images per chip formation. Their treatments by the digital image correlation will lead to identify the kinematic field.

One of the binding points in the choice of the frame rate is that its increase is accompanied by a loss of spatial resolution. So, we must look for a good compromise. However, the performance of high speed cameras differs according to their models. For that, presenting the evolution of the spatial resolution depending on the frame rate turns out interesting to make a choice on this couple. Figure 1 describes this evolution for different models of FASTCAM high speed cameras.

Figure 10: Evolution of the spatial resolution depending on the frame rate for different FASTCAM high speed cameras models: FASTCAM a) SA3, b) APX-RS, c) SA5 and d) SA-Z.

Each scored point is a point with a couple of frame rate and spatial resolutions (horizontal and vertical spatial resolution). In these points, the frame rate belongs to $\{6.10^3, 10^4, 1.5.10^4, 2.10^4, 3.10^4, 4.10^4, 6.10^4 \text{ and } 7.5.10^4\}$. The corresponding minimum horizontal spatial resolution is 512 pixels and the minimum vertical is 280 pixels.

A good compromise will have to take place to make a choice on this couple. The choice on a frame rate must be in adequacy with the number of images required to apply the digital image correlation.

- Theoretical number of images per chip formation

The cutting speeds V_c as well as the frame rate f_{aq} will influence the number of images per chip formation. Thus, the relationship between these parameters must be established to estimate the number of images per chip formation. To apply the digital image correlation, a sufficient number of images must be guaranteed. To determine this relationship, two hypotheses will be posed:

- The width of a segment is supposed to be equal to the feed [Pottier 2014].
- The chip formation speed is assumed equal to the cutting speed.

As a result, the number of images per chip formation is given by:

$$n = \frac{f_{aq} \times a}{V_c}$$

Where a denotes the feed.

For a feed of 0.25mm and for different cutting speeds, the number of visual images per chip formation is given by the following figure:

Figure 11: Evolution of the number of images per chip formation as a function of cutting speeds and frame rate: a) Cutting speeds $\in [5..30\text{m/min}]$ and b) Cutting speeds $\in [15..60\text{m/min}]$.

More the cutting speed increases, more the frame rate of the camera must be increased to guarantee a sufficient number of images that can reveal the strain evolution during the adiabatic shear band formation. Example, for the Ti-6Al-4V and at $V_c = 6\text{m/min}$, 45 images were sufficient [Pottier 2014] to describe the evolution of the kinematic fields during adiabatic shear band formation by applying the digital image correlation. Figure 11.b) shows the number of images per chip formation for relatively large cutting speeds ($\geq 15\text{ m / min}$). With high cutting speeds, the use of a high speed camera that can reach high frame rates is necessary (100000fps with a spatial resolution of $640 * 280$ pixels for the case of the FASTCAM SA-Z camera).

The following table summarizes the anticipated optical parameters of the high speed cameras that will be used for orthogonal cutting tests with cutting speeds of [$5..60\text{m / min}$].

Test	V_c (m/min)	Camera FASTCAM ...	Spatial resolution		Frame rate (fps)	Nbr of images for each chip segment
			H (Pixels)	V (Pixels)		
Test 1	5	SA5	832	448	$20 \cdot 10^3$	~60
Test 2	10	SA5	768	320	$30 \cdot 10^3$	~45
Test 3	15	SA5	768	320	$30 \cdot 10^3$	~30
Test 4	20	SA-Z	512	456	$75 \cdot 10^3$	~56
Test 5	25	SA-Z	640	280	$100 \cdot 10^3$	~60
Test 6	30	SA-Z	640	280	$100 \cdot 10^3$	~50
Test 7	40	SA-Z	640	280	$100 \cdot 10^3$	~37
Test 8	50	SA-Z	640	280	$100 \cdot 10^3$	~30
Test 9	60	SA-Z	640	280	$100 \cdot 10^3$	~25

Table 3: Anticipated optical parameters of the high speed cameras with respect to the cutting speeds.

3.2.3 Temperature measurement

For temperature measurements, we will use the thermal camera FLIR SC7000. The optical parameters are given in the following table:

Integration time (μs)	Frame rate (fps)	Spatial resolution (pixels)
50	600	$160 * 128$

Table 4: Optical parameters of the thermal camera FLIR SC7000.

Calibration method of the IR camera

Infrared camera cannot directly measure the temperature. Each camera detector returns an electrical voltage expressed by default in Digital Levels (DLs), using a transfer function known as Non Uniform Correction (NUC) [Soler 2018]. After that, to relate the digital levels (DLs) with the radiation temperature RT , it is necessary to use a blackbody. Therefore, the IR camera calibration requires two steps:

- 🌈 Step I: NUC calibration; more details on this step can be found in [Harzallah 2018].
- 🌈 Step II: Thermal calibration; it requires the use of a blackbody to relate the digital levels (DLs) with the radiation temperature.

To obtain real temperature T from the radiation temperature, the following equation is mostly used:

$$\frac{1}{T} = \frac{1}{RT} + \frac{\lambda}{C_w} \ln(\varepsilon)$$

Where C_w denotes the second radiation constant and ε is the emissivity of a surface at the λ wavelength. Therefore, emissivity of material must be determined function of temperature and wavelength.

Emissivity of the studied materials

Emissivity of material depends from the surface topography but mainly from the surface temperature and the wavelength of the emitted radiation. For Ti-6Al-4V samples, the normal spectral emissivity function of the temperature [273°C..854°C] and the wavelength [5 μ m..20 μ m] is given in the following figure:

Figure 12: Normal spectral emissivity of Ti-6Al-4V samples [González-Fernández]: a) function of wavelength and b) function of temperature.

The emissivity dependence from temperature and wavelength for the case of Inconel 718 material can be found in [Del campo 2010]. For Al7075, it can be found in [Wen 2005, Wen 2006a and b]. Several mathematical form of emissivity models were examined in [Wen 2006b] to study the effect of surface roughness on the emissivity of aluminium alloys.

4. Implementation of the experimental protocol

The bench that will be used for our first orthogonal cutting tests is the bench developed in [Blanchet 2015]. The workpiece is clamped in a mobile vise. The cutting speed is transmitted from the motor to the vise through a ball screw. The tool is maintained fixed and mounted on a dynamometer.

4.1 Tools implementation

- Vise fixture

The Rohm 7201 vise is mounted on a rectangular aluminium piece as shown in figure 13. This piece is an intermediate piece between the vise and the screw of the linear axis.

Figure 13: Vise fixture in the orthogonal cutting bench.

- Dynamometer fixture

The bottom surface of the Kistler 9257B dynamometer must be:

1/ Perpendicular to the upper surface of the vise.

2/ Placed at a distance of 16mm from the upper surface of one of the jaws. With this distance, the workpiece can not touch the lower surface of the square.

4.2 Cameras fixture

The micrometer table [Figure 14] is placed on a single-leg stand with adjustable height. On the micrometer table is mounted the modular tray that carries the VISIR and the two cameras: the high speed camera FASTCAM SA5 and the thermal camera Flir Sc7000. The lighting of the viewing scene is done using a LED that sends a clogged light.

Figure 14: Setting up the VISIR device with the high speed and thermal cameras.

The lens is X15 magnification. It is placed at a distance of 23.7mm from the tip of the tool.

4.3 Adjustment

- Placement of the workpiece:

It consists of positioning the workpiece in the middle relative to the cutting face of the tool. It is made by moving the table of the bench along the Y axis. No instrumented verification has been done.

- Setting up the feed:

A comparator is used for this setting. It is placed as follows:

- The tip of the comparator touches the lower surface of the set square.
- The magnet part is fixed on a surface that moves with the table along the Z axis.

Quality of the image: To ensure a good quality of the image, a quick stop test is done first. An adjustment on the distance between the lens and the tip of the tool is made using the micrometer table.

During the tests, a blur on the chip was observed. It is observed on some visual images in the film of the high speed camera. To overcome this problem, it was necessary to:

- Decrease the feed from 0.25mm to 0.15mm.
- Add a second lighting system.

This blur persists over some visual images obtained with tests on Ti-6Al-4V workpiece with a lamellar microstructure. This can be attributed to off-plan chip motion.

4.4 Operative and optic parameters

- Operative parameters:

The tests were carried out on two Ti-6Al-4V workpiece with two different microstructures: Lamellar and globular. The used insert is H13A with a cutting angle of 0 ° and a clearance angle of 11°. It is mounted on a 0 ° insert holder. The cutting angle is 0°, the cutting speed is 5m/min for the tests from 2 to 8 and the feed is 0.15mm [Table 5]. The following table summarizes the realised tests, the microstructure of the workpieces, the cutting parameters and the encountered problem during the tests.

Test	Ti-6Al-4V Microstructure	Cutting angle	Cutting speed (m/min)	Feed (mm)	Encountered problem
1	Lamellar	0°	12	0,15	-----
2					
3					
4					
5					
6	Globular	0°	5	0,15	Frame rate of the IR camera
7					
8					

Table 5: The realised tests with the operative parameters.

- Optical parameters :

The used optical parameters of the FASTCAM SA5 high speed camera and the FLIR SC 7000 IR camera are given in the following tables:

Integration time (µs)	Frame rate (fps)	Spatial resolution (pixels)
50	20000	512*512

Table 6: Optical parameters of the FASTCAM SA5 high speed camera.

Integration time (µs)	Frame rate (fps)	Spatial resolution (pixels)
50	600	160*128

Table 7: Optical parameters of the FLIR SC7000 IR camera.

5. Results and analysis

5.1 Cutting efforts

- Orthogonal cutting configuration :

We denote by:

- V_c : Cutting velocity.
- λ : Cutting angle.
- α : Clearance angle.
- a : Feed.
- a_c : Chip width.
- l_c : Chip contact length.
- ϕ : Shear angle.

The orthogonal cutting configuration with the previous mentioned parameters is described in the following figure.

Figure 15: Orthogonal cutting configuration.

In this section, the results that will be presented corresponds to orthogonal cutting tests on Ti-6Al-4V workpiece with globular microstructure. The operative cutting parameters are as follow:

- $V_c=5\text{m/min.}$
- $\lambda=0^\circ.$
- $\alpha=11^\circ.$
- $a=0,15\text{mm.}$

- Cutting efforts:

Three cutting efforts components are interesting to be analysed in this cutting configuration: The cutting force [Figure 16.a], the feed force [Figure 16.b] and the torque around Y axis [Figure 16.c]. Validation of numerical models is based at first on comparison between the obtained numerical and experimental cutting efforts. Their evolution function of time is given in figure 16.

Figure 16: Evolution of the cutting forces function of time.

Periodic fluctuation of the cutting forces can reveal the instability nature of the cutting process of Ti-6Al-4V. This can be traced back to the process of chip formation. When segmented chip forms, the chip thickness will periodically change. Theoretically, increasing the chip thickness can decrease the shear angle, leading to the increase of the cutting efforts [Zhang 2013]. Figure 16 describes the cutting efforts evolution over time. This periodic fluctuation could mainly be caused by the segmented chip formation process. With orthogonal cutting experiments on Inconel 718 made by [Zhang 2013], it can be found that the fluctuation frequency of the cutting efforts agrees well with the segmentation frequency.

The mean values of the obtained cutting efforts are given in the following table:

Cutting efforts	F_c [N]	F_f [N]	M_y [N.m]
Mean values	400	30	5

Table 8: Mean values of the cutting efforts.

The cutting time T between two cutting efforts peaks is equal to:

$$T=0,0016s$$

Hence, the fluctuation frequency of the cutting effort is equal to:

$$f=625Hz$$

5.2 Kinematic field measurements

- As-captured image:

The images were captured using the high speed camera FASTCAM SA5 with a frame rate of 20000fps and a spatial resolution equal to 512*512 pixels. From a reference image, we could extract some parameters:

- The size of one pixel.
- The size of the field of interest.

The field of interest [figure 17] is the region in which we could follow the different stages related to the chip formation. It contains the adiabatic shear band and a portion of the secondary shear band.

Figure 17: Extracted parameters from the as-captured visual image.

From this figure, we note that the feed $a=0,15\text{mm}$ corresponds to a height of 116 pixels. Hence, 1 pixel is equal to $1,29\mu\text{m}$. The field of interest is equal to $199*152$ pixels. We deduce that it corresponds to a $0,25*0,19\mu\text{m}^2$.

- Grey level:

In an image, each pixel has a grey level. The grey level histogram can be defined as the number of pixels corresponding to each grey level. The grey level histogram related to the field of interest described in figure 17 is given in the following figure:

Figure 18: Grey level histogram.

As it is shown, dispersion of pixels over the grey levels is high. This could damage the quality of the image. Therefore, applying the digital image correlation will be difficult. For that, correction of the quality of the images using numerical treatments is required.

- Numerical correction of the visual image quality:

The numerical correction of the visual image quality is composed of 2 steps:

- Step I: Normalizing the histogram; it consists on transforming the grey level (f) of each pixel so that the image uses all the dynamics of representation. This step is based on the following equation:

$$f_{\text{new}}[i, j] = (f[i, j] - N_{\text{min}}) \frac{2^D - 1}{N_{\text{max}} - N_{\text{min}}}$$

Where D denotes the dynamic; $D = \log(N_{\text{max}} - N_{\text{min}})$; N_{max} is the maximum grey level and N_{min} is the minimum grey level.

(i, j) are indexes related to the image matrix.

- Step II: Equalizing the histogram; this step aims to minimize the pixels dispersion over the grey levels. It is based on the following equation:

$$f_{\text{new}}[i, j] = (f[i, j] - N_{\text{min}}) \frac{HC(f(i, j))}{w \times h}$$

Where (w, h) is the image dimensions.

$HC(x)$ is the pixels rate which the grey level is less than x . It is given by the following equation:

$$HC(x) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^x H(i)}{w \times h}$$

This part which is related to the numerical correction of the visual image quality is yet under investigation. The main question that can be posed is how to apply this numerical correction to the visual image.

- Vic 2d:

The kinematic field measurement will be performed using Vic 2d software. The defined parameters are:

- Subset = 29 pixels.

- Step = 7.

The subset size (in pixels) and the step meaning are described in the following figure.

Figure 19: Defined parameters in Vic 2d

- Kinematic field results

Recently, the formation process of segmented chip is described mainly by three stage [Pottier 2014] which were defended by [Harzallah 2018]. This three stage are as follow:

- Stage 1: Compression stage.

- Stage 2: Shear stage at the level of the adiabatic shear band: In this stage, we could notice a crack initiation followed by its propagation. [Harzallah 2018] found that the crack propagation could be retired if the compression is higher than the shear.

- Stage 3: Ejection stage.

Due to the bad quality of the obtained image, we will present in this document the kinematic field results related only to the stage 1 [Figure 20]. With a cutting speed equal to 5m/min and a frame rate 20000fps, 22 visual images are sufficient to describe the compression stage during chip formation.

With the previous mentioned cutting parameters ($V_c = 5m/min$ and $\lambda=0^\circ$) and from figure 19, image 22, we found that the maximum shear strain during the first stage of chip formation is equal to:

$$e_{xy} = 0,166$$

Figure 20: Evolution of the shear strain during the first stage of chip formation.

- Comparison:

The obtained shear strain fields will be compared with those resulting from the orthogonal cutting experiments made in [Harzallah 2018] and with a cutting speed equal to $V_c=3\text{m/min}$ and a rake angle equal to $\lambda=0^\circ$. The associated shear strain field is given in figure 21.

Parameters which are defined in Vic 2d are as follow:

- Subset 43.
- Step7.

With a frame rate equal to $f_{aq}=6000\text{fps}$ and with the previous mentioned cutting parameters, 14 visual images were sufficient to describe the shear strain field evolution during the first stage of chip formation. In this case, the maximum shear strain in the first stage is equal to:

$$e_{xy} = 0,365$$

This value is higher than the value obtained with a cutting speed equal to $5\text{m/min} > 3\text{m/min}$. It could be attributed to the feed. In [Harzallah 2018], the feed is equal to $a=0,25\text{mm} > 0,15\text{mm}$. This difference in shear strain field could be also due to the difference in microstructure. The microstructure of the Ti-6Al-4V workpiece in [Harzallah 2018] is "equiaxed". In our case, the Ti-6Al-4V workpiece is with globular microstructure.

Figure 21: Evolution of the shear strain during the first stage of chip formation related to the experiment made in [Harzallah 2018] using Vic 2d.

6. Conclusion

This document was set to describe the employed methodology for temperature and kinematic field measurement during orthogonal cutting test. Results about the cutting efforts and the kinematic fields at the first stage during chip formation were presented.

- With a cutting speed $V_c=5\text{m/min}$, a feed $a=0,15\text{mm}$ and a cutting angle equal to 0° , the mean value of the cutting force is equal to 400N.
- With the previous mentioned parameters, the maximum shear strain at the first stage during chip formation is equal to 0,166.

These results needs to be compared to be able to judge its accuracy. More orthogonal cutting tests with different cutting parameters will be performed for this purpose. Furthermore, the sensitivity of the shear strain value over the subset will be studied in the future work.

With a bad quality of the obtained image, results about the other two stages couldn't be identified. This bad quality could be attributed to:

- Weak lighting system: the lighting power per sub-millimetre area should be studied for this reason.
- Bad chemical attack of the workpiece: the spending time in the chemical attack could be the reason for a bad quality of the obtained image.

Working on the last two points will be necessary to ensure a good quality of the image that can give results about the other two stages of chip formation.

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List of acronyms

AA = Aluminum alloy

AS = Advancing side

CT = computer tomography

ESR = Early stage researcher

FSW = Friction Stir Welding

HAZ = Heat affected zone

IR = Infrared camera

RS = Retreating side

TMAZ = Thermo-mechanically affected zone

UBx = University of Bordeaux

WP = Work package

Summary

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Deliverable 3.2

The ENABLE (European Network for Alloys Behavior Law Enhancement) project's scope is the development of new solutions for forecasting and mastering processes relevant for all factories using metallic alloys, proposing a rethink of the usual process simulation methods. In this context, the duties of the three ESR of the WP 3 involved in the project are defined and divided in a certain number of tasks to be achieved for a pre-defined date during the whole project. Each ESR has to provide the deliverables according to the timeline defined in the ENABLE project. The deliverable is a document that contains all the information related to the progression and/or the achievement of a certain task. The drafting of those documents is proof of the work carried out by the ESR and its host institution during a certain period of their thesis for the achievement of the pre-agreed tasks.

The deliverable 3.2 "*Measuring temperature and kinetic fields during FSW, AM, machining and broaching*" represents the second step for the WP3 and ESR 7,8 and 9 must setup suitable system measurements to feed the WP2 with data gathered during specific experiments defined during the definition of the standard cases for each process (see Deliverable 3.1). The data collected during the experiments for each process will then be processed and compared by WP2 to validate and/or improve their models and simulations.

1 Objectives of Deliverable 3.2

For ESR 8, the Deliverable 3.2 consists in the kinetic and temperature field measurements during Friction Stir Welding process. These measurements are attended to rebuild temperature gradient and material flow in the

welding. The goal is to provide accurate values of temperature, strain and strain rate during the process in the welding seam. The information and data gathered during this experimental phase will be then provided to the WP 2 to feed the simulation methods.

The measurements will be performed on a certain configuration defined after the first experimental campaign. The configuration obtained during the first experimental campaign, where feed rate and rotating speed have been varied, were: sound weld, weld with internal defects and welds with external defects. Once the measurement systems for the temperature and kinetic fields will be set up, the previously identified configuration will be tested to obtained data in all the different possible outcomes. Moreover, the development of reliable measurement systems will allow reproducing conditions simulated by other researchers of WP2 to assess the quality of the results obtained through their simulations.

2 Temperature field measurement

Over the years, temperature measurement has been considered as one of the ways to improve knowledge about the process for two reasons: firstly, monitoring the temperature make possible the understanding of certain outcomes in terms of weld quality and microstructure; secondly, the rebuilding and understanding of the thermal field developed in the material is fundamental for the modelling of the process. The complex thermal history undergone by the material during the welding is obviously dependent on process parameters and its severity results in better or worse joint characteristics.

Several attempts have been made for the thermal measurements in the friction stir welding. Indeed, FSW is a 3D confined process where the tool is plunged in the welded material during the welding. Consequently, the tool/material interaction is not directly accessible during the process. Because of this inability to follow the material during the process, an accurate thermal acquisition, especially in the welding area (nugget and TMAZ), is a huge obstacle and for this reason, the welding community is still working on it. Different techniques have been used to measure temperature during the process. The most successful, even with their limitations, are certainly thermocouples and infrared cameras.

2.1 State of the art

2.1.1 Thermocouples embedded in the workpieces

Thermocouples embedded in the workpieces are one of the most applied solutions. This type of sensors has guaranteed the possibility of obtaining information on the temperatures reached in the welded plates in various areas even if with some drawbacks such as, positioning, impossibility to use the welded parts later because they are damaged and risk of damage

to the sensor or change of position if inserted in the stirred zone.

In the various studies already available in the bibliography, the thermocouples have been placed at a different thickness in the plates, distances from the welding line and configurations. In some cases, the thermocouples have been inserted vertically from the bottom of the plates [1-3] Fig.1(a) or from the top [4] Fig.1(b) and fixed at different heights and distances from the welding line. In the same way, in other available works, thermocouples have been placed horizontally in the welded plates through holes drilled along the thickness of the plates [2,5] Fig.2. In the case of very small thicknesses (around 3 mm or less), the thermocouples have been also fixed between the sheets to be welded and the backing plate and therefore in contact with the lower surface of the pieces to be welded [6,7] Fig.3.

Figure 1 - Thermocouples fixed vertically in the workpieces a) [2], b) [4].

Figure 2 - Thermocouples fixed horizontally [2].

Figure 3 - Thermocouples in contact with the bottom surface of the workpieces [5].

Overall, in some works differences in the peak temperature measurements between AS and RS have been found [2,5], while in others not neglectable distinctions have been detected [8]. Measurements performed in different thicknesses along the width of the weld have not shown significant variations in 8 mm thick plates of AA6061 [9].

The main problem with this solution is the impossibility of following the temperature range in the mixing zone. Thermocouples fixed at a distance from the welding line less than or equal to the radius of the pin will inevitably end up being smashed when the pin passes and/or moved from their initial position, losing important information. In addition, thermocouple measurements are strongly influenced by their positioning, which is why the repeatability and comparison of two measurements made with the same thermocouple setting are really complicated.

2.1.2 Thermocouples embedded in the tool

During the years of research focused on a better understanding of the FSW process, several laboratories have researched a method that would allow measuring the temperature inside the stirred zone during the process. A solution proposed and already used in several studies and the use of one or more thermocouples inserted directly into the FSW tool [2,10,11]. Also, in this case, the positioning of the thermocouples is fundamental and the information that can be obtained will inevitably be influenced by the area where the thermocouple is inserted into the tool. Several research groups have carried out measurements with thermocouples inserted in the tool, both in the pin and in the shoulder, with different settings, on aluminium alloys [2,10]. The changes made to the tools for the appropriate allocation of thermocouples can be different as shown in Fig.4.

Figure 4 - Thermocouples embedded in the tool a) [2] , b) [10].

Regardless of the different structure of the whole system, even the positioning of the thermocouples is obviously a very delicate aspect and even a small difference can provide different information. The results showed contradictory values for the thermocouples placed in the shoulder and in the pin. Highest values of the temperature in the shoulder have been found in [10] (Fig 4b) and vice versa for [2] (Fig 4a). This result showed how the measurement is affected by the system and the positioning of the thermocouple inside the tool. The use of a single thermocouple in the tool was also used to evaluate the influence of feed rate, rotating speed and axial force on the temperature obtained within the stirred zone for different aluminum alloys [11].

2.1.3 IR camera

As an alternative to thermocouples, non-contact measuring systems such as infrared cameras have also been used over the years [12-14]. This type of solution, like thermocouples, has a number of complications to ensure accurate measurement and some limitations due to the typical support systems used in FSW. The angle of incidence of the infrared camera with respect to the welded plates, the high reflectivity of the aluminum alloys, the tool and support system, combined with the confinement of the process and the limits on the positioning of the camera due to the presence of the lateral clamps mean that the implementation of this type of system is certainly not simple and practical. Other few attempts have been made with infrared cameras [12].

A really interesting result with IR camera is shown in [12] where the authors estimate the temperature during the whole process thanks to an IR camera. The IR camera was mounted integral with the machine head, in this way the area of interest was always focused on a window with the

some distance from the tool. The area of interest and the measured

Figure 5 - Temperature measurement through IR camera [12].

temperature during the welding are shown in Fig. 5.

In a different work, to avoid the problems related to the positioning of the camera and the obstruction of the clamps, a special support system as shown in Fig. 6 has been realized [13]. This vertical support system, suitably made with slots in order to have access to the welded plates on their lower surface with a perpendicular angle of incidence, has made it possible to obtain measurements during welding on both sides, AS and RS (Fig.7).

Figure 6 - Support system to measure with IR camera from the bottom surface of the welded plates [13].

Figure 7 - Measurement during the process with IR camera [13].

2.2 Experimental phase

Before the setting up of the temperature measurement system, as already reported in Deliverable 3.1, a quite large range of parameters, feed rate and rotating speed, have been investigated. The set of configurations tested are listed in Table 1 and the outcomes are synthesized in Fig. 8.

Axial force (kN)	Feed rate (mm/min)	Rotating speed (rpm)
5.5	60	800 - 1000 - 1200 - 1400
5.5	120	800 - 1000 - 1200 - 1400
5.5	180	1000 - 1200 - 1400 - 1600
5.5	240	1000 - 1200 - 1400 - 1600
5.5	300	1000 - 1200 - 1600 - 1800
5.5	360	1000 - 1200 - 1400 - 1600 - 1800 - 2000

Table 1 - Process parameters combination.

Figure 8 - Weldability window for the cases studied.

As displayed in Fig. 8 four different outcomes have been obtained from the first tests:

- non-defective joints;
- joints with internal voids;
- slight lack of fill after a first part of the joint that seemed not defective;
- deep cavity with chip formation on the retreating side;

According to these results, accurate temperature measurements will be carried out once the measuring system has been set up.

The systems chosen for these measures are thermocouples placed at the bottom surfaces of the welded plates, between the plates and the backing plate and IR cameras. The choice has been based on the state of the art on temperature measurement in FSW and as well the knowledge in monitoring in the team. Through the information that will be obtained with these sensors, an attempt to trace the temperatures inside the nugget zone will be performed.

2.2.1 Thermocouples

Some measurements using thermocouples after the first modification to the support system have been performed. To avoid extra modification of

the welded plates and considering the small thickness of the plates, the first attempts have been carried out fixing the thermocouples on the bottom surfaces of the plates. To integrate the thermocouples in the system some modification on the backing plate were required. The system is characterized by an aluminium single-piece with a slot in the centre of it for the entire length that represents the space necessary for a steel anvil that retains heat being characterized by a much lower thermal diffusivity than aluminium (Fig. 9).

To enable thermocouples to pass through the system and touch the plate to be welded, some modifications have been performed on the anvil. On the original rectangular steel mono-bloc, some slots on the bottom and holes perpendicular to the sides parallel to the welded plates have been made, as shown in Fig. 10. The thermocouples wires have been fixed in the slot and fixed in the holes through a high-temperature cement (resistant to temperatures above 800°C). Only the tip of the thermocouple exits the hole to ensure contact with the welded plates (Fig. 11).

Figure 9 – Support system with the steel anvil as backing plate.

Figure 10 - Anvil modification (slots and holes).

Figure 11 - Tip of the thermocouples.

First measurements with this configuration of 5 thermocouples with pyramidal arrangement with respect to the direction of welding, were carried out. From the measurements carried out, two out of the five thermocouples did not provide reliable results and therefore were not considered.

The accuracy of the measurement in this configuration is another problem. First of all, the plates to be welded must be properly secured by the clamping system to prevent the plates from slipping, which, due to the type of configuration chosen, leads to a change in the position of the thermocouple resulting in measurements different from those desired. To avoid this problem, a slight groove in the support system may be provided to prevent this displacement of the thermocouple tip. In the Fig. 12 the curves of the measurements made during the one test are presented. The acquisition was carried out with a DAQ at a frequency of 75 Hz to be divided on the number of thermocouples used.

Figure 12 – a) Measurements in the test at 60 mm/min and 800 rpm; b) Thermocouples positioning;

Soon, other attempts will be made to ensure accurate and repeatable measurements to compare the temperatures reached in the various configurations.

2.2.2 IR cameras

Coupled with thermocouple measurements, two infrared cameras are available to complete the acquisition of temperature measurements. The tools available are as follows:

- CEDIP Jade III MWIR retrofitted FLIR Titanium SC 7000;
- *FLUKE Ti401 PRO Thermal Camera*;

Considering the size and the models the two IR cameras will be used for 2 different purposes. The FLIR will be used as a fixed device to detect the thermal field at the end or at the beginning (plunging + first part of the weld) of the welding. The second one, smaller and more flexible, will be mounted on the ACTEMIUM spindle with support to follow the whole welding. The design and 3D conception of the support are still under investigation and then some tests will be necessary to manage the vibration problem that affects the process. Also, for this camera fixed on the support the possibility of placing it in the front and rear part of the joint will be taken into consideration. In both cases, measurement on the two sides, AS and RS, will not be possible because of the horizontal clamps which obstruct the view and therefore do not allow images to be captured in these areas.

The first acquisitions have been made in the last month of July only using the FLIR camera with the configuration showed in Fig. 13.

Figure 13 – IR camera position during the acquisition.

The welded plates have been with black paint to increase their emissivity to approximately 1. Due to the limited vision due to the whole system (robots, spindle, tools etc.) the angle of incidence was set at 47° . These first tests were used for calibration, to evaluate the quality of the measurements made with the IR camera comparing them with measurements obtained with thermocouples. In any case, some indications have already been obtained by working in relative by evaluating the different temperatures obtained in the various cases tested. In Fig. 14, some frames took from one weld and some measurements are shown.

Figure 14 – a) Temperature measurements for two points on the plate in the configuration 60 mm/min and 800 rpm; b) Position of points whose temperature profiles are shown in a).

In Fig. 15 the information gathered with thermocouples and IR camera is represented for one of the tested configurations.

Figure 15 – Peak temperatures measured with thermocouples and IR camera for 60 mm/min and 800 rpm

3 Kinetic field measurement

The understanding of the material flow inside the nugget and thermo-mechanically affected zone represents another key point in the complex mechanisms of the friction stir welding process. The comprehension of what happens during material-tool interaction, from when a layer comes into contact with the tool to when it is released behind it, represents the crucial point to improve the general knowledge of the process for two reasons:

- 1) the understanding of phenomenology in terms of material flow, can be clarifying about the origin of defects such as voids, lack of penetration etc.;
- 2) displacement measurements and estimation of strain and strain rate would guarantee the possibility of obtaining reliable models and thus make the FSW process simulations more consistent.

Unfortunately, considering that FSW is a confined process that takes place beneath the shoulder of the tool during the whole process, after 30 years of research in the domain the two points mentioned above are still under investigation. Significant improvement in the process' comprehension has been made among the years regarding the material flow thanks to several studies using markers inside the nugget zone. On the contrary, few jobs have been carried out in the search to access, even if partially, the welding area during the process (tools without pins, tools without shoulder etc.). Obviously, the reason is to be attributed to the complexity of this type of solution as each small modification could in fact distort the process giving rise to results that are not representative of FSW phenomena.

3.1 State of the art

3.1.1 Marker techniques

Among the years, several authors have widened the knowledge about the material flow in FSW using a different type of markers. In early studies, Colligan [15] analysed the material flow placing steel shot tracers in the abutting edges of friction stir welded plates (Fig. 16), through post-mortem analysis of the cross-section.

Figure 16 – Steel shot tracers positioning in the transverse plane perpendicular to the welding direction [15].

The author pointed out the existence of complex material flows with part of the welded material actually mixed and dragged by the pin rotation and the rest simply extruded around the pin.

The differences in the material flow depending on its position in FSW (AS or RS and considered depth), through an artificial thicker oxide layer between the abutting edges, have been explained by Zeng et al. [16] evaluating the oxide layers flow from post-mortem analysis of the joints (Fig. 17).

Figure 17 – Post-mortem analysis of the oxide layers flow [16].

Schmidt [17] focused on the material flow in friction stir welding placing a thin copper layer in the same direction and orthogonally to the feed of the tool (Fig. 18). The behaviour of copper foils in the various arrangements was studied by traditional metallography as well as X-ray and CT. Also, attempts to clarify the flow during the process were made by Seidal et al. [18] with AA5454 markers placed alternatively on the advancing and retreating side along the welding line (Fig. 19). The final position after welding of the markers was detected by metallographic means.

Figure 18 – Configuration tested with different placement of the copper foils [17].

Figure 19 – Positioning of the AA5454 marker along the length and thickness of the welding plates [17].

All the above-presented works gave a strong contribution to the comprehension of the material flow in FSW. All those studies are based on the post-mortem analysis of the welded plates (metallography, X-ray, CT) and the presence of an external material during the process. These two factors have some drawbacks. The post-mortem analysis can give useful information comparing the initial and final position of the external material, without considering what is effectively happening during the process. Differently, the presence of the external material could influence the “real” material flow of the welded material during FSW giving information that may not fully represent the actual process.

To overcome the limitations of post-mortem analysis of the joints, Morisada et al. [19] have rebuilt the material flow during FSW following the displacement of a tungsten particle, using two pairs of X-ray transmission real-time imaging systems (Fig. 20). The existence of rotational flow perpendicular to the welding direction generated by the rear of the pin, that prevents the defects formation in the nugget zone, has been demonstrated. To date, few studies of this type “real-time” have been carried out. The reason for the scarcity of this type of studies is certainly

to be found in the need for particular and very expensive measurement systems.

Figure 20 - Sketch of the acquisition system of the steel shot tracer movements [19].

3.1.2 Other solutions

Several authors have investigated the material flow during FSW using two different alloys [20-22]. The advantage of using two different materials, that react differently from etching, is represented by the possibility to observe the mixing through traditional metallographic observations.

The influence of the process parameters on the effective mixing during the process and the genesis of the banded structure typical in the longitudinal sections in FSW have been investigated in [22], welding AA7075 and AA2024 plates and using the "stop action" (Fig. 21).

Among the years, some authors also tried to investigate the material flow using plasticine instead of alloys during FSW [23,24]. Even if the thermo-mechanical behaviour of plasticine, in terms of thermal cycle and strain, during the process cannot be compared to alloys used in FSW, these works gave information regarding the material flow. In [24], through the comparison between welding performed on aluminium alloys and plasticine, the authors showed clearly the existence of two different flows each one driven by the pin and shoulder, respectively (Fig. 22).

Figure 21 – Longitudinal sections of joints performed with the “stop action” technique [22].

Figure 22 – a) Plasticine b) Aluminium alloy [24].

Other authors, performed FSW on transparent plastic material to observe the material flow during the process using a high-speed video camera (Fig. 23) [25, 26].

Figure 23 – Experimental setup in [26].

3.1.3 Strain and strain rate estimation

In addition to investigation on the material flow, numerous works have been focused on the determination of the strain rate during FSW. Several different techniques have been used to predict the strain rate and different results have been obtained during the years confirming that a well-established and reliable technique, which can provide in-situ visualization and measurement of the strain rates has not yet been identified.

In early studies, the strain rate has been estimated through microstructure observations [27]. In the specific, the authors estimated the strain rate between $1.6\text{-}17.3\text{ s}^{-1}$ at 1500 rpm and $300\text{-}720\text{ mm/min}$ by correlating the final grain size in the SZ with the Zener-Holloman parameter ($Z = Z = \dot{\epsilon} e^{\frac{Q}{RT}}$) where $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the strain rate, T is the temperature in K, R is universal gas constant and Q is activation energy.

Tracers have also been used not only to understand the material flow but also to estimate the strain rate [19]. Following the displacement of a tungsten particle during FSW of Al1050 alloy at 1000 rpm and 400 mm/min , the authors estimated the strain rate at 13.4 s^{-1} (Fig. 24).

ND: Normal direction of the A1050 plate, TD: Transverse direction of the A1050 plate
 IP: Initial position of the tracer, FP: Final position of the tracer

Figure 24 – Movement of the tungsten particles for various rotating speed [19].

The strain rate has been also evaluated experimentally employing the “stop action” technique to freeze the material microstructure [28]. The deformed dendrites have been used as flow markers for deformation analysis. The authors estimated that in the leading transitional zone, material deformed up to a strain of 3.5 with a strain rate of up to 85 s^{-1} before entering into the thread space.

Recently, also the particle image velocimetry (PIV) has been used to understand the material flow and measure the strain rate around the tool during FSW [29]. PIV technique is an in-situ technique for the visualization of material flow and estimation of strain rate during the process. In numerical simulation material rheology during FSW has been described as non-Newtonian, incompressible and viscoplastic. For this reason, the authors simulate the FSW process using a transparent material representative of a non-Newtonian, incompressible and viscoplastic behaviour. The material flow has been visualized using spherical glass tracers in a transparent viscoplastic fluid. Strain rate was estimated to increase from 8 to 44 s^{-1} with an increase in the rotating speed from 75 to 425 rpm (Fig. 25).

Figure 25 – a) Schematic representation of the flow measurement using PIV system, b) images of the tracers' particles in two consecutive instants [29].

Besides the few experimental attempts to predict the strain rate during FSW, several computational works have been carried out to predict this quantity during the process, with a significant variety of tools and materials and are resumed in Table 2.

Technique used	Maximum Strain rate (s^{-1})	Materials and processing parameters	Source
Numerical 3-D heat flow model	a)1.6-10.3 b)1.7-17.3	a)6082 Al alloy b)AA7108 Al alloy 1500 rpm, 300-720 mm/min	[30]
3-D Numerical simulation	45	AA6061 344 rpm, 95 mm/min	[31]
3-D Numerical modelling	35	Stainless steel 300 rpm, 101 mm/min	[32]
3-D Numerical analysis	25	Mild steel	[33]

		450 rpm, 25 mm/min	
Steady state, Eulerian, CFD model	20-350	AA5083-O, AA2219-T87, AA7050-T751 54-844 rpm, 755 mm/min	[34]
3-D coupled visco-plastic flow and heat transfer model	9	AA2524, 300 rpm, 126 mm/min	[35]
2-D finite element simulation	87	5083 Al, 1500 rpm, 50.8 mm/min	[36]
3-D thermo-mechanically coupled Finite element method	a)34.8±5.2 b)122.5±11.2	AZ31B cast alloy a)600 rpm, 100/min b)2000 rpm, 700 mm/min	[37]

Table 2 – Summary of the strain rate values obtained through simulation [29].

3.2 Experimental phase

The experimental work focused on the material flow during FSW will move along two parallel paths, both with the aim of proposing something innovative that can actually provide some more information on the behaviour of the material during FSW.

The first path concerns the experimental observations of the material flow during the process. As already seen in the previous paragraphs, one possible way of investigation is the employing of tracers during the process and consequent post-mortem analysis. Although already well researched in previous years, the use of tracers is definitely something that can be easily implemented in our system and that, proposed in an alternative way, could continue to increase knowledge about the material flow conducting post-mortem analysis with both metallographic and CT techniques. Considering the results obtained during the first experimental campaign, further investigation about the existence of the different material flows, driven by the pin and the shoulder, respectively, could be further studied using tracers. A first idea, currently under investigation, is the placement of a copper sheet between two overlapping plates (Fig. 26).

Figure 26 – Copper foil different positioning to study the material flow.

Depending on the starting position of the copper foil along with the thickness, the trace of copper particles could be found randomly in the cross-section of the joint. Considering the different influence of the pin and shoulder on the material depending on the area, interesting information could be gathered. Also, to expand the study, rather than using the same type of aluminium alloy in the sandwich structure proposed in Fig. 25, an AA6082 plate could be used to obtain other information. Taking advantage of the different reaction of the microstructures of the two alloys to the etching with Keller's reagent, more information about the flow could be achieved. The sections could be obtained not only with simple cross-sections with respect to the direction of welding but also with longitudinal sections and parallel to the plates for more information. This analysis could improve the surprising results obtained in the first analysis, giving more insights regarding the occurrence of flow-related defects during the FSW.

Another possibility in the same direction is the insertion of prismatic markers horizontally with respect to the welding line of different extension arranged progressively with respect to the feed of the tool (Fig. 27).

Figure 27 – Horizontal tracers along the welding line.

Again, even with this configuration, through post-mortem analysis, more information can be gathered. Obviously, the added material must not have characteristics such as to alter the process and therefore the flow but at the same time visible with the techniques that will be used for the subsequent analysis. Further investigations will be made to find the best solution.

Despite the use of tracers, another way to get more information about the material flow could be direct observation of it during the process. Considering the confined nature of the FSW process, the direct access to the material flowing around the tool is for sure not possible in the traditional asset with the support system, backing plate, clamps and the alloys plate to be welded. However, other studies in the past have already confirmed that by slightly modifying some components of the system or the process, without completely changing the nature of the process, some observations have been possible. This direction, although complicated, will certainly be deepened looking for different solutions that can really propose something different. In fact, even just a few small observations could still bring so much to a process still so misunderstood with FSW because, as already mentioned, of the confinement of this welding operation. One idea could be to attempt to use a tool without a shoulder. As is well known, however, the shoulder plays a double fundamental role in the process, i.e. it brings heat through the friction developed at the interface with the workpiece and then the containment of the material inside the welding seam. Then these two roles could be performed by two substitutes such as an alternative heat source that, although for a few mm could allow the execution of a small joint FSW without shoulder and a transparent material overlapped to the welding plates could not only

contain the material but also allow the view of what happens on the surface. A schematic representation is proposed in Fig. 28.

The execution even of few mm of FSW in this configuration could provide useful insights from two point of view. Firstly, the theorized cyclical deposition of layers by the pin could finally be seen and experimentally proven. Secondly, the stirred zone will be affected only by the pin. The analysis of the cross-section of an FSW joint manufactured without the shoulder may isolate the effect of the pin on the material flow elucidating aspects that are still unclear today (onion rings, recrystallization etc.). Clearly, this as others, are ideas that are still under investigation to propose something innovative.

The second path consists of the estimation of the strain rate in FSW. As already proposed above, several techniques have been already used and different results have been proposed. Unfortunately, often those tests differ between them for welded material, workpiece geometry, tool, system

Figure 28 – Modified system for material flow observations.

etc. and comparison has not been possible. However, the significant differences found between all the different methods (experimental, computational, microstructure) confirmed that a reliable method has not been found yet. The aim will be to propose another way or improve some other method already used, to finally get a better estimation of the strain rate in FSW making a step ahead in the knowledge of this technique.

Among the several techniques analysed, the PIV seemed really promising and further investigation this direction will be done in the next months. A better estimation of the strain rate in FSW will finally give the possibility to improve the model and simulation of the process itself and will also allow prediction on the final microstructure obtained in the stirred zone depending on the tool, material, welding parameters etc.

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Deliverable 3.2 - ESR 9

1. Melt pool dynamics

In the Selective Laser Melting process, the melt pool dynamics and physics is a very complex phenomenon which has not yet been fully understood. Figure 1, depicts all the physical phenomenon that occurs during laser-material interaction and these influence the process stability and quality of the final component fabricated by Selective laser melting. Identification and evaluation of this phenomenon are of great interest. As the selective laser melting is very complex, it is very difficult to measure and observe the occurrence physical phenomenon at the melt pool level. It has been studied by many researchers with the help of numerical modeling such as multiscale modelling .The powder bed is irradiated by a laser beam during heating, whereby the photon energy is transformed into thermal energy by absorption. Generally, photons are absorbed within the first few nanometers of the surface of the material [1]. In contrast to opaque continuous material, the powder bed allows for deep penetration of the laser due to multiple reflections at the surface of the material powder [1-2]. The distribution of the absorbed thermal energy depends on the relative packing density and reflectivity of the powder material within the top powder layers.

The penetration depth of the laser beam strongly depends on the laser power [3], which has to be optimized for better material health. As most of the processing material is prone to oxidation, the building chamber is either filled with inert gas or kept at vacuum (EBM). The photons are deflected and scattered due to their interaction with the material's atomic structure.

Due to thermal radiation, convection, and evaporation of volatile elements, a heat loss is observed with biquadratic, linear, and exponential depending on the surface temperature of the material, respectively. In SLM, heat convection between the material and the shielding gas also occurs whereas heat convection to the surrounding atmosphere is negligible in EBM because of the vacuum in the build chamber. The absorbed thermal energy is further distributed into the material due to heat conduction, and temperature peaks at the surfaces are reduced which significantly depends on the thermal diffusivity of the material and the sintering grade of the powder bed. Therefore, it is very difficult to print material with high reflectivity and poor thermal conductivity. To reduce the chances of part failure due to poor heat flow, preheating is applied, the base temperature of the powder bed is elevated, simplifying melting and reducing temperature gradients during manufacturing. As the powder bed has low heat conductivity as compared to the bulk material, support structures play a crucial role for heat during the subsequent manufacturing and increase the thermal conductivity [4].

Melt pool formed due to laser-material interaction has complex thermo-physical phenomenon due to convection, phase transformation, conduction, surface tension variation, interaction with surrounding, etc. Convection depends on the viscosity of the melt pool which in turn proportional to the temperature (which is proportional to energy density) and is driven by external forces like gravity, buoyancy, surface tension, capillarity, Marangoni effects, and evaporation pressure. Based on the process and the material, these phenomena have varying impacts on the final quality of the component. The melt pool lifetime is extremely short,

viscosities of the melt pools are very low, and gravity plays a minor role compared with the roles of the other forces [5]. Thermal expansion of the material during heating induces buoyancy and exerts thermal stresses. The high surface tension and the wettability of the metals result in a smooth surface for stable melt pools whereas, unstable melt pools are split up, and the surface tension causes the formation of single melt beads [6–8]. Marangoni convection forces induce fluid motion away from the high-temperature peak in the center of the melt pool and increase heat distribution [9,14]. The melt pool fluid motion is additionally driven by the recoil pressure resulting from material evaporation. This phenomenon results in the formation of the keyhole porosities, in which the laser beam penetrates into the material up to certain layer thicknesses, forming a vapor capillary (see picture)[28]. The selective evaporation of the volatile elements also changes the local and global material composition [10]. Due to rapid heating and cooling of the material induces stresses in the surrounding material that can partially relax due to repetitive heating and cooling cycle during the process [11]. The residual stresses due to high thermal gradient inside the component are the main reason for distortions and part failure [12,17]. Based on the temperature gradients and the processing temperature, a specific microstructure evolves [10,13,15-16]. Due to the layer-wise processing, repetitive heat treatment of the heat-affected zone around the melt pool may change the microstructure by solid-state phase transformations. Fabrication of fully dense parts strongly depends on the high flowability of the powder which depends on the powder properties such as surface topology, size distribution, and shape, is necessary to achieve the high relative density of the powder bed [19].

Figure 1: Thermo-mechanical physical phenomena of the melt pool during printing.

2. Melt pool simulations

During selective laser melting, a laser source moves over the unsolidified material and causes thermal expansion in the heat-affected zone. Surrounding, solidified regions will be exposed to compressive stresses due to thermal expansion of the heat-affected area leading to plastic strains which will accumulate with every added layer and remain after the finishing of the

process. These residual plastic strains are considered as one of the main cause for residual stresses and resulting deformations.

The accumulation of residual strains can be modeled in a layer-by-layer fashion via the Finite Element Method and the application of the Inherent Strain (IS) Method. The idea is to determine (experimentally or numerically) representative values of these residual strains that occur in the actual manufactured part and apply them in each layer in the simulation model.

Note: in reality, there are several actual layers within a modeled hex-mesh layer.

However, via determining of representative IS for a given geometry and given machine settings, these strains can be applied per hex-mesh layer to “mimic” the accumulation of very localized residual strains phenomenologically.

This activation and simulation process is repeated in a (hex-mesh) layer-by-layer fashion until all layers are being simulated. In a final step, the boundary conditions for consideration of fixation of the part to the building plate are changed to simulate the deformation after the part is being removed from the building plate.

Using Additive Lab software, which is a strong numerical simulation tool for additive manufacturing, we simulated the melt pool area for AlSi10Mg. As the software is calibrated for the only limited number of materials, we choose AlSi10Mg alloy. From the figure, the melt pool dimensions were measured in x, y, and z-direction which is as follows: [0.0825,0.0566,0.0258]. The temperature observed at the center of the melt pool is 1260 °C (Figure 2). It should be noted that actual temperature may be different from the simulated temperature due to lack of consideration of the evaporation and radiation during the melting process. By assuming that the melt pool is half of an ellipsoid, the volume can be calculated from the measured x,y and z dimensions. The volume of the melt pool is $0.504 \text{ e}^{-03} \text{ mm}^3$. With scanning power and an absorption coefficient, the body heat flux can be calculated which

Figure 2: Melt pool simulation for AlSi10Mg.

serves as the input for thermo-mechanical macro-layer analysis. The next thing is to determine

the exposure time at each point. As seen in the figure, the material is exposed to heating above the melting temperature of the AlSi10Mg for about 0.00018 seconds (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Temperature vs time plot at the centre of the melt pool in simulation model.

3. Melt pool monitoring sensitivity

3.1. Introduction

The LBM is one of the few AM process that allows the manufacturing of three-dimensional structures of metallic components using high power laser [20-22]. Solidification is obtained by melting and fusing the successive layers of metal or alloy powders by supplying very high thermal energy supplied by the laser. The laser beam is deflected on to the powder materials through the Galvano scanners which scan each layer based on the cross-section of the parts calculated from the CAD model. Once a layer of powder is scanned by the laser, a new layer of powder is applied through the recoating mechanism and the process of solidification with the laser is repeated. The LBM process is typically carried out in inert atmosphere to prevent oxidation of the material and chemical reactions between the molten material and the environment.

Recently, Selective laser technology has evolved drastically and the demand for better quality control system has been on hype. This led to many types of research in the field of in-situ monitoring for a better quality of finished parts to detect anomalies easily. There are various process parameters such as high power, high scanning speed, bed powder spreading, high layer thickness, etc. which can significantly let too many other defects in the finished part. The various process parameters which can significantly influence the quality of the product are summarized by Eric Lacoste et. al. [23]. Due to the layer-wise principle of the process, these defects are very hard to detect after the part is completed. To ensure internal quality and better detectability, expensive techniques such as computed tomography is done. Since CT is expensive and time-consuming, its use is limited. However, limitation in part size and

quality, CT is not a viable solution to quality inspection. Therefore, the need for an on-line monitoring system is inevitable and it led to the development of many on-line systems on commercial machines. As the field of in-situ monitoring is in the amateur stage, a lot of work still must be done. In the near future, there will be a possibility to provide online feedback to a machine about the concerned defect so that the process parameters can be adapted according to that. This will be revolutionary in the series production of the parts using additive manufacturing technologies.

Kruth et al. at KU Leuven installed the in-situ monitoring system on its in-house built Selective laser melting machine. The in-situ monitoring system consists of a CMOS camera and a photodiode which measures the radiation in the wavelength of 700-940 nm range. Similarly, other research institutes developed optical hardware based on their need, for example, setup developed by Lott et al. [24]. The coaxial setup developed by Lott et al. is quite like the setup developed by Kruth et al. but their setup uses the illumination of the laser beam to study visualize the melt pool dynamics. Doubenskaia et al.[25 -28] developed a pyrometer consisting of two photodiodes with a detection range of 900-1700 nm. All the systems have a lot of similarities, however, most of them don't interpret the results instantly. The system developed by Kruth et al. uses the FPGA chip to process the signal coming out of the photodiodes immediately. The same principle is used by SLM solutions but with two photodiodes with a detection range of 1100-2400 nm.

3.2. *Experimental*

To easy detection of anomalies during the process, reference data for each material should be generated. To generate reference data for AlSi7Mg0.6 (elemental composition is given below), the various types of artificial defects were created based on the varying process parameters such as power, scanning speed, hatch distance, etc. as shown in the table below. The volume energy density is calculated based on equation 1 where P, V, DT, and H denotes the power, scanning speed, layer thickness and hatch distance, respectively.

$$\text{Volume energy density (J/mm}^3\text{)} = P/(V*DT*H) \quad \text{(Equation 1)}$$

The varying parameters are listed below:

Varied Parameter	Values	Unit
Power	300, 350 and 400	W
Scanning speed	1200, 1400, 1650 and 1900	mm/s
Hatch distance	0.13, 0.26 and 0.52	mm
Layer thickness	0.03	mm
Scanning strategy	Stripes	-

The elemental composition of AlSi7Mg0.6:

Element	Si	Mn	Ni	Ti	Cu	Pb	Mg	Zn	Sn	Others
%	6.5-7,5	<0.35	<0.15	<0.25	<0.2	<0.15	0.2- 0.65	<0.15	<0.05	<0.15

The AlSi7Mg0.6 samples were fabricated by SLM280HL equipped with a melt pool monitoring system, laser power monitoring system and layer control system. The build platform was preheated to 200 C prior printing of the jobs to minimize the residual stresses. The Oxygen content in the build chamber was reduced to less than 0.1% and filled with Ar gas to provide an inert atmosphere for printing. The particle size distribution of the AlSi7Mg0.6 used for printing was 20-63 μ m. The relative density of the as-built samples was measured based on the Archimedes principle using methanol as the liquid. For optical microscopy, samples were mirror polished on SiC paper with different grades and the optical microscopy was conducted on Leica systems microscope.

3.3. Results

The aim of varying process parameters is to create different situations visible by comparing the response from the melt pool monitoring system. Even if the process parameters are similar, the photodiode response varies which is dependent on the local area scanned. Other factors such as machine environment, dirt on laser glass, etc. can also affect the signal detected by photodiodes but in our study, we have opted it out. We assume the factors have minimal effect on the MPM system.

3.3.1. Varying Hatch distance

The effect of standardized volume energy by varying hatch distance on the MPM system was detected and evaluated. The three different hatch distance chosen are 0.13, 0.26 and 0.52 mm. The evolution of MPM signal for first five layers is shown in figure 4. It is observed that for the first layer the mean of thermal counts is relatively higher for both ADC1 and ADC2 whereas after 3rd layer the thermal counts seems more constant. The reason for higher values for the first layer is due to local conditions for heat conductivity. Based on volume energy, the highest values of the first layer varies with hatch distance as shown in figure 4. The highest value for both ADC1 and ADC2 was observed for hatch distance of 0.26 mm.

Figure 4: MPM signal varies with layer number for different hatch distance.

3.3.2. Varying Energy density

Small cylinders with a diameter of 15mm and height of 8mm were fabricated by SLM using varying power (300,350 and 400 W) and scanning speed (1400, 1650 and 1900 m/s). It

Figure 5: (a) Density values Vs Volume energy density (b) MPM signal Vs Volume energy density.

could be clearly observed (figure 5) that the signal varies with the volume energy density calculated by equation discussed earlier. For ADC2 values, there is an increase in the thermal counts with an increase in energy density whereas, for ADC1, there are significantly lower values observed for the energy density of 54 J/mm³. (Note: the mean of 5 top and 5 bottom layers is considered as there is no significant difference in the values)

3.3.3. Lack of fusion

There are lots of defects that could occur in the as-built part based on many process phenomenon, lack of fusion is one of the defects that are most commonly observed in the parts due to lack of enough energy to melt the whole layer or if there is bad powder layer spreading. To animate the lack of fusion defects we tried to fabricate hollow parts as shown in figure (intersection of part). Based on the number of missing layers (1,2,4 and 8), we try to observe the MPM system sensitivity which is shown in figure 6. It is observed that the thermal counts for ADC2 increases with an increase in the number of missing layers and the maximum value observed for the 4 layers. In contrary to ADC2, the ADC1 values remains constant and doesn't vary too much. The reason behind the difference in the ADC1 and ADC2 values is due to different sensitivity detection range of the photodiodes. The Archimedes density values for different missing layers (1, 2, 4 and 8) are 99.76% , 99.76%, 99.70% and 99.60%, respectively. The higher ADC2 values explain the presence of lack of fusion defect in the part due to missing layers.

Figure 6: (a) Intersection of CAD file (b) MPM signal.

3.3.4. Down skin effect

One of the advantages of selective laser melting is to fabricate complex parts, overhang structures as well. Normally, overhang structures below 40 deg are easy to fabricate without support structures. As the overhang structure have different thermal conditions compared to the rest part due to the low heat conductivity of the powder. To ensure the detectability of this phenomenon by the monitoring system we fabricated a part with an overhang as shown in figure 7. We compared the two different layers (overhang layer with normal layer) as shown in the figure 7. Layer 295 denotes the last layer before the overhang layer whereas layer 296 represents the overhang. It is clearly noticed that there is a significant increase in the signal for both photodiodes and it varies with different energy densities as well.

Figure 7: (a) Schematic diagram depicting CAD design (b) MPM signal for two different

3.4. Conclusion

The commercial MPM system is able to detect the drifts during the process such as overhang, lack of fusion and change in volume energy density during the process. Easy post-processing and generating a reference have the capability to improve the in-situ monitoring and reliability of the process. The future work is planned to solve the big data problem.

4. Residual stresses

The inverted L shaped cantilever specimen as shown in figure 8 (left) is used to estimate the residual stresses in the printed part. The overhang structure is supported by the thin pillars for better heat conductivity. The end of the cantilever is fixed with the build plate. This type of has been studied by many researchers for various materials [29-33]. Two cantilevers were printed each in X and Y direction to study the effect of build orientation on the residual stresses. The relaxation of stress along the entire length of the specimen contributes to the deformation, which is measured by 3D scanner GOM as shown in figure 8 (right). The measurement data points are taken along the length of the cantilever. Post printed the

cantilevers were cut by wire electric discharge machining with the there rectangular base still connected to the build plate. The wire EDM technique was used so that no new stresses are introduced in the cantilever which can be easily done through conventional cutting. It could be easily seen the deflection along the x plane is greater than the y plane. The parabolic curve fitting is seen in the figure 9 for both planes along the vertical top surface of the cantilevers. This is an easy method to predict the residual stresses in the part quantitatively. For more accurate results, expensive techniques such as hole drilling, x-ray diffraction, etc. are more viable.

Figure 8: CAD file of cantilever (left) and GOM of wire EDM cut cantilever (Right).

Figure 9: Deflection of cantilever along length in x and v plane.

5. *Machine learning*

As discussed earlier, the large amount of data obtained from the melt pool monitoring system which is difficult to process. In recent years, a lot of research has been done on data analytics and classification techniques in additive manufacturing. To address the current problem of big data in additive manufacturing, there are a variety of machine learning (supervised and unsupervised) methods are applied. Among them, K-means clustering, wavelet analysis, and neural network methods are capable of potentially automatically discovering features and patterns in a random collection of data points. The focus of this study is to extract the correct feature from the big data which represents the small variation in the data arising from the complex thermo-physical behavior of the melt pool during printing. It is important to understand that, each data point from the photodiode signal represents the complex physics of the melt pool dynamics which ultimately decides the quality of the end product. In this study, we tried to extract the abnormality in the data and predict the quality of the product based on the mechanical properties of the part. For this, the k-means algorithm is chosen in this study since it is efficient in classifying the data points with a predefined number of clusters and very fast and robust for a large amount of data. It can be used to analyze the efficiency of the clustering quantitatively. Also, k-means clustering has been extensively used in a range of applications due to its simplicity and ease of implementation compared to other clustering algorithms. The principle of the k-means clustering is discussed below.

5.1. *Feature Extraction*

Feature extraction is the first step in applying k-means clustering for big data. As the amount of data is very big in our case, it is essential to apply dimensionality reduction on the data. The following approach is used:

- Photodiode data for each layer was extracted using the decoder provided by SLM solutions.
- The means and standard deviation of each layer are calculated.
- It is verified that the standard deviation correctly captures the abnormality in the data as compared to the mean.
- Removal of support structures data points from the data set is performed.
- An $n \times 2$ size matrix is formed, where n is the number of layers and two columns store the values for both photodiodes.

Artificial defects were created in the part to study the sensibility of the photodiodes to capture the abnormalities during the process. Figure 10 shows the mean and standard deviation for the various types of artificially created defects. It could be observed that if the support structure data points are not eliminated from the data sets it could significantly affect the final result. From the standard deviation, it is possible to extract the correct layer position of the defect. Figure 10 (left) shows the failure of the building part as the down skin area was not fully supported for better heat conductivity and eventually leads o failure due to unstable melt pool. It is clearly captured in the standard deviation of the photodiode signal. The initial bump

in both the graphs is due to the support structures which are eliminated in the feature extraction process.

Figure 10: mean and standard deviation profile for overhang structure (left) and lack of fusion case (right).

K-means clustering is one of the unsupervised machine learning technique, used for unlabeled data (data without categories and groups). The aim of K-means algorithm is to define groups in the data, where the number of groups is represented by the variable K. It works iteratively to assign each data point to one of K groups based on the data features. Each data point is clustered based on feature similarity. The output of the K-means clustering algorithm are:

1. The centroids of the K clusters, which is further used to classify new data.
2. Training data labels (each data point is assigned to a single cluster).

Instead of defining groups before analyzing the data, clustering allows to find and analyze the groups that have formed organically. The variable K describes how the many clusters can be formed.

Each centroid of a cluster is a collection of feature values which define the resulting groups. Examining the centroid feature weights can be used to qualitatively interpret the type of group each cluster represents.

5.2. Algorithm

The K-means clustering uses the iterative method to produce a final result. The algorithm inputs are the data set and the number of clusters K. The data set is a collection of features as described above. In our case, the extraction of the correct feature from the data is the most important step which will define the final result of the algorithm. The algorithm starts with the initial estimation for the K centroids, which can either be randomly selected from the data set or randomly generated. The algorithm then iterates between two steps which are as follows:

1. Data assignment step:

Each centroid defines a specific cluster. Each data point in the data set is assigned to its nearest centroid, based on the squared Euclidean distance. More formally, if c_i is the collection of centroids in set C, then each data point x is assigned to a cluster based on

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{C_i \in C} \operatorname{dist}(C_i, x)^2$$

where $\operatorname{dist}(\cdot)$ is the standard (L_2) Euclidean distance. Let the set of data point assignments for each i^{th} cluster centroid be S_i .

2. Centroid update step:

In this step, the centroids are recomputed based on the mean of all data points assigned to that centroid cluster.

$$C_i = 1/|S_i| (\sum_{X_i \in S_i} X_i)$$

The algorithm runs iteratively between above discussed two steps until the stopping criterion is satisfied which is no data points change clusters, the sum of the distances is minimized, or some maximum number of iterations is reached.

Finally, the algorithm converges to a result. The obtained result may be a local optimum which means it may not be necessarily the best possible outcome. It can be improved with assessing more than one run of the algorithm with randomized starting centroids may give a better outcome but it costs computationally. The new unlabeled data can be labeled based on the trained data set. The accuracy and success rate of the algorithm depends on the amount of training data. These types of algorithm require an enormous amount of data for training to achieve good results.

5.3. Case Study

An SLM 280HL machine was used to build tensile samples consisting of approximately 6000 layers. All the samples for this study were produced from a single batch of AlSi7Mg0.6. Typical properties include high strength, excellent corrosion resistance. It has a wide range of applications within the industry and is suitable for thin-walled components. In particular, it is highly suitable for processing and has corrosion resistance. Its excellent welding characteristics and resistance to cracking makes it an ideal material for Additive Manufacturing. Samples were built in a layer-wise fashion on a substrate plate. The plate is connected to an elevator which moves vertically downwards, allowing the controlled deposition of powder layers at 30 μm intervals.

Post-build the samples were removed and machined for tensile tests as per ASTM E8M as described earlier. Figure1 shows the MPM system from SLM 280HL. The illustrated Melt Pool Monitoring system uses two photodiodes with different sensitive areas. The signals are permanently taken up by the individual photodiodes, forwarded to an ADC (analog-digital converter) and provided in an FPGA (field-programmable gate array). ADC 1 is associated with photodiode 1 and ADC 2 is associated with photodiode 2. In favor of the signal-to-noise ratio measurements result by averaging hundreds of individual measurements. Depending on the machine and optical system set up as well as taking into account two different photodiodes the signal-to-noise ratio is at present up to 10. The measured value of the thermal emission of the photodiode 1 and 2 are output to these present x/y-coordinates (16-bit) in parallel as well as the laser on/off signal from the FPGA to the PC every 10 μ s. The FPGA controls the correct timing of the input signals, other potential operations and the subsequent measurement task of 10 μ s. All data packages of a measurement task will be stored per layer in a data file and can be traced back clearly due to time function and are able to the readout. After completion of the exposure of the current layer, a new file is created automatically.

Using the MPM system, the aim is to extract significant information about build quality from the photodiode measurements. In this study, quality is defined using the Yield Strength of each bar. It is assumed that the YS value of the part captures the internal defects of the part as well. So the parts with no defect or relative fewer defects will show similar properties compared to parts with more defects in them.

During printing, the x and y position of the laser was collected alongside the measurements from 2 photodiodes sensors (sample frequency equal to 100 kHz, resulting in approximately 400 GB of data per build). The feature extraction from such big data as described earlier.

Based on the features extracted, the k-means algorithm was applied for the 20 samples and training the algorithm. It was noticed that the data is distinguished between two separate clusters which are clearly observable in figure 11. Cluster 1 denotes the sample with inferior properties compared to cluster 2. All the samples in the cluster 1 have YS in the range of 260-280 MPa whereas for cluster 2 the range is 280-285 MPa.

Figure 11: K-means cluster for training data.

After training, it is very important to test the algorithm with the new data set to verify it. For the test, 12 samples were used as test data and passed through the trained algorithm. It was

Figure 12: K-means clustering for test data.

noticed the samples were being classified into respective clusters based on the features marked as asterisk in figure 12. The success rate of the algorithm was observed to be 84%. A large amount of data is always beneficial for training the algorithm to get better results. The future work will be to train the algorithm with a large amount of data and considering other criteria which will be a better representation of the defects in the samples.

6. *Effect of the scanning strategy*

6.1. *Experimental Methodology*

6.1.1. *Material and processing parameters*

The composition of AlSi7Mg0.6 powder with a particle size of 20-63 μm from SLM Solutions, used for this study. The experiments were carried out on the SLM 280HL machine using the process parameters listed below.

Element	Si	Mn	Ni	Ti	Cu	Pb	Mg	Zn	Sn	Others
%	6.5-7,5	<0.35	<0.15	<0.25	<0.2	<0.15	0.2-0.65	<0.15	<0.05	<0.15

6.1.2. Density measurements

Porosity and density of samples were measured and calculated Archimedes principle. Total porosity was calculated by multiplication of bulk density (BD) and total cumulative volume (TCV), where TCV equals to measured pore volume divided by the weight of the sample. Apparent density was calculated according to $1/((1/BD)-TCV)$.

6.1.3. Mechanical testing

Three tensile test specimens were fabricated for each test case, according to ASTM- E8 / E8M standard [33]. Tensile tests were performed at a crossheads displacement rate of 1 mm/min using an Instron 4500. Vickers hardness tests were conducted according to ISO 6507-1 [35] using a 1 kg load on a Zwick hardness Tester. An average hardness value was calculated for each sample using 3 indentations taken along the width of the 30 × 30 × 10 mm block cross-section. For each test case, two cylindrical blocks with 16mm dia and 120 mm length were manufactured to be used for residual stress measurement (see figure 13). Residual stresses were measured on the surface and at a depth of 2 mm into the sample at 3 different locations (figure 14-right) with an average error of 7% in case of 95% confidence interval, using X-ray diffraction technique (equipment- Figure 14) according to DIN EN 15305:2009. Samples were chemical-etched for 2mm depth to minimize the effect on residual stresses.

Figure 13: Residual stress samples (left) and ASTM E8M tensile sample profile (right).

Figure 14: X-ray diffraction equipment (left) and measurement area marked on samples (right).

6.2. Effect of the scanning strategy

The effect of different scanning strategies on mechanical properties and residual stresses was determined. The table below list the nomenclature and scanning strategy used in this study. There are two types of scanning strategies, stripes and chessboard were studied with varying chessboard island size and stripes size with the rotation angle of 45°, 67°, and 90° between consecutive layers. The 45°, 67°, and 90° represent the orientation of each over-building layer by 45°, 67° and 90° respectively. Chessboard strategy represents dividing the build area into small blocks. Each block is scanned from inner to outer fashion. The description of the sample nomenclature in the below table is as follows: S denotes the scanning strategy (S=strips and C=chessboard), followed by the size of the stripes and chessboard blocks and the end letter denotes the rotation angle between the alternative layers.

Sample ID	Scanning Strategy	Size	Rotation (°)
S_5_67	stripes	5mm	67
S_10_67	stripes	10mm	67
S_15_67	stripes	15mm	67
S_10_90	stripes	10mm	90
S_10_67	stripes	10mm	67
S_10_45	stripes	10mm	45
C_2*2_no	chessboard	2mm*2mm	-
C_3*3_no	chessboard	3mm*3mm	-
C_5*5_no	chessboard	5mm*5mm	-
C_10*10_no	chessboard	10mm*10mm	-
C_5*5_45	chessboard	5mm*5mm	45
C_10*10_90	chessboard	10mm*10mm	90

It can be observed from figure 15 that the stripes (S_5_67, S_10_67, S_15_67,) and chessboard blocks (C_5*5_no, C_2*2_no, C_10*10_no, C_3*3_no) size do not affect the yield strength of AlSi7Mg0.6 samples considerably and the small variation can be attributed to the stochastic nature of the process. Chessboard scanning strategy did not show any clear trend in % elongation values with increasing Chessboard size. From Fig, it is observed that there is a small correlation between % elongation and % porosity. The % elongation is significantly increased and % porosity subsequently decreased for chessboard strategy with applying rotation between the layers to 45o. Overall it could be observed that the chessboard strategy with no rotation shows the inferior properties compared to stripes.

Scanning strategy did not have any considerable effect on the Vickers hardness of the samples as shown in figure 16, as the microstructural analysis of the samples, needs to be studied. The slightly lower values of test case C_5*5_no, C_2*2_no, C_10*10_no, and C_3*3_no may be a result of higher porosity levels (can be seen in fig). Test case S_10_67 was printed two times on two different build jobs, yet the properties are not the same which can be seen in fig and fig. The variation could be due to an error in measurement or the different thermal conditions during printing. The printing time for the build job was considered the same. The microstructural analysis will be performed to study for the cause.

It could be observed in the figure 17, the ductility and tensile strength of the chessboard strategy without rotation are even inferior to the as casted AlSi7Mg0.6 properties, whereas the properties for stripes with rotation between layers shows the better mechanical properties.

Figure 15: Mechanical properties for varving scanning strategies.

Figure 16: Vickers hardness values for varying scanning strategies .

Figure 17: Tensile strength Vs Ductility for different cases.

6.3. Residual stresses

Residual stresses are the internal stresses present at equilibrium in a manufactured part. As we know, the selective laser melting introduces residual stresses in the part. These stresses if not optimized could lead to part failure. The state of the residual stresses in the part is the result of the entire manufacturing scheme (the processes). During the manufacture of the part, uncontrolled relaxation of the residual stresses can cause detrimental deformations. After being put into service, any residual stresses present at the end of manufacturing are added to the external mechanical stresses. As a result, they affect the part's lifetime. In general, residual compression stresses at the surface are beneficial and cause an increase of resistance to fatigue or to corrosion under stress. Tensile residual stresses are penalizing and correspond to areas at risk of premature failure.

The test pieces used for the study of residual stresses are cylinders with a diameter of 16 mm and length of 120 mm (attached from the manufacturing plate).

The residual stress measurements are done for test case S_10_67 build in two build jobs. As earlier, it was noticed that despite having the same processing parameters the mechanical properties vary much. Therefore, the residual stress profile for these two samples was studied. The samples were kept in as build condition so there is no stress relief occur.

The measurements are taken as follows (figure 14-right):

- one area in the middle of the test piece;
- one area 55 mm from the middle (start edge)
- one area 55 mm from the middle (end edge)

For each area, the residual stresses are measured (figure 14-right) at the surface with post-processing and at 2mm depth. For 2mm depth, the samples were electrochemically etched so that the stress profile is least affected. For each area, two measurements were done: in 0° and 90°.

It can be observed that the maximum residual stresses observed are in the middle of the sample for the test cases. The residual stress in 90° is higher compared to 0°. The residual stresses are much smaller than the yield strength of the samples which is 296 MPa and 302 MPa, respectively. For both of the samples, it was observed that the compressive residual stresses at the surface are greater than the compressive stresses at 2mm depth (figure 18 and 19). As has been reported earlier, compressive residual stresses at the surface transform into the tensile residual stresses inside the sample. Therefore it is very essential to study the overall profile of the samples. The explanation for maximum residual stresses at the middle of the sample could be due to rapid cooling of the melt pool at the middle as compared to the edges. As the rapid cooling of the melt pool gives very limited time for the material to relax and it develops maximum stresses.

Figure 18: Residual stresses for at different locations for test case S 10 67 (1).

Figure 19: Residual stresses for at different locations for test case S 10 67 (2).

7. Future work

The future work will be concentrated on the study of the following topics:

1. Training the machine learning algorithm k-means clustering with more data.
2. To improve the machine learning algorithm with better feature extraction technique and comparing the results with the existing technique.
3. With current data processing, it is viable to do cluster the samples based on the mechanical properties. But there is a lot of work need to be done to locate the exact location of the defect in the manufactured part.
4. As we have seen, the residual stresses inside the part are more complex and critically affect the part quality. Therefore, the overall profile of the stress inside the part need to be studied.
5. Effect of scanning strategies on the residual stress profile will be studied.
6. Correlation of residual stresses between as-built and post machined parts will be studied.
7. Machine learning on another type of data such as IR images will be applied and a correlation between different monitoring techniques will be studied to improve the quality of the part and online monitoring of the process.

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